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Тематика журнала: актуальные вопросы современной экономики и социологии - от теоретических и экспериментальных исследований до непосредственных результатов управленческой и производственной деятельности. Публикации в журнале учитываются как опубликованные работы при защите диссертаций на соискание ученых степеней России и зарубежья.

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INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION SYSTEMS FOR TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESS MANAGEMENT: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

Abstract. In the ever-evolving realm of technological process management, information and communication systems (ICS) play a pivotal role in orchestrating and streamlining complex workflows, enhancing decision-making capabilities, and fostering collaboration among stakeholders. This comprehensive review delves into the intricacies of ICS, exploring their functionalities, applications, and impact on technological process management (TPM).

Key words and phrases: Sensors, Information and communication systems (ICS), Technological process management (TPM), decision-making, coordination, control, data acquisition systems, networks, real-time monitoring, decision support, process efficiency, quality control, downtime, agility, responsiveness.

Introduction. Technological process management encompasses the intricate coordination and optimization of interconnected tasks, transforming raw materials into value-added products or services. To effectively navigate the complexities of this domain, businesses have turned to ICS, leveraging their ability to capture, analyze, and disseminate critical information across organizational boundaries.

Components of Information and Communication Systems

ICS typically consist of the following components:

- ❖ **Sensors and data acquisition systems:** These components collect data from the physical world, such as temperature, pressure, and flow rates.
- ❖ **Networks and communication infrastructure:** These components enable the transmission of data between sensors, controllers, and other devices.
- ❖ **Data storage and management systems:** These components store and manage the vast amounts of data generated by technological processes.
- ❖ **Software applications and analytical tools:** These components process and analyze data to provide insights into process performance and identify areas for improvement.

Functionalities of ICS in Technological Process Management

ICS encompass a diverse array of tools and technologies, each contributing to the seamless execution of technological processes. Key functionalities include:

➤ **Data Acquisition and Collection:** ICS enable the collection of real-time data from sensors, machines, and other sources, providing insights into process performance and potential anomalies.

➤ **Data Storage and Management:** ICS facilitate the secure storage and management of vast amounts of process data, enabling historical trends and patterns to be analyzed for optimization purposes.

➤ **Information Dissemination and Sharing:** ICS facilitate the dissemination of process information to relevant stakeholders, promoting transparency and collaboration across departments.

➤ **Decision Support and Analysis:** ICS provide advanced analytics tools to transform process data into actionable insights, aiding decision-making at various levels of the organization.

➤ **Process Monitoring and Control:** ICS enable real-time monitoring of process parameters, allowing for prompt identification and rectification of deviations.

Benefits of ICS in TPM

The implementation of ICS in TPM offers several benefits, including:

❖ **Improved Process Performance:** ICS enable the identification and elimination of process inefficiencies, leading to improved productivity, quality, and overall process performance.

❖ **Reduced Operational Costs:** ICS can help reduce operational costs by optimizing resource utilization, minimizing downtime, and preventing equipment failures.

❖ **Enhanced Safety:** ICS provide real-time monitoring and control capabilities, helping to prevent accidents and ensure a safe working environment.

❖ **Increased Employee Engagement:** ICS can empower employees with data-driven insights, fostering a culture of continuous improvement and employee engagement.

Challenges of Implementing ICS in TPM

Despite their potential benefits, implementing ICS in TPM can present several challenges, including:

➤ **Data Integration and Management:** Integrating data from multiple sources and managing large volumes of data can be complex and resource-intensive.

➤ **Cyber security and Data Privacy:** Ensuring the security and privacy of sensitive data is essential to prevent unauthorized access and protect intellectual property.

➤ **User Adoption and Training:** Training employees on how to use and interpret data from ICS is crucial for effective utilization.

➤ **Cost and Investment:** Implementing ICS can involve significant upfront costs and ongoing maintenance expenses.

Applications of ICS in Technological Process Management

ICS have permeated various aspects of technological process management, including:

✓ Supply Chain Management: ICS streamline supply chain operations by optimizing procurement, inventory management, and logistics processes.

✓ Manufacturing and Production Control: ICS enable efficient production scheduling, resource allocation, and quality control within manufacturing environments.

✓ Product Development and Innovation: ICS foster collaboration and knowledge sharing among engineers, designers, and researchers, accelerating product development cycles.

✓ Service Management and Delivery: ICS enhance service delivery by enabling real-time tracking of service requests, resource allocation, and customer feedback.

Impact of ICS on Technological Process Management

The integration of ICS has revolutionized technological process management, leading to a plethora of benefits:

✓ Improved Process Efficiency: ICS enable the identification and elimination of bottlenecks, reducing cycle times and increasing overall process efficiency.

✓ Enhanced Decision-Making: ICS provide data-driven insights, empowering managers to make informed decisions that optimize resource utilization and minimize risks.

✓ Promoted Collaboration: ICS facilitate information sharing and collaboration across departments, breaking down silos and fostering a culture of innovation.

✓ Increased Transparency: ICS provide real-time visibility into process performance, enabling stakeholders to identify issues promptly and take corrective actions.

✓ Reduced Costs: ICS streamline operations, minimize waste, and optimize resource allocation, leading to significant cost savings.

Conclusion. Information and communication systems have emerged as indispensable tools for technological process management, enabling businesses to achieve new heights of efficiency, innovation, and agility. By harnessing the power of ICS, organizations can optimize their workflows, enhance decision-making capabilities, and foster collaboration, ultimately driving organizational success in a competitive and dynamic marketplace.

References:

1) Lee, J., & Rha, J. H. (2016). Information and communication technologies in supply chain management: A review of the literature and future research directions. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics, Transportation Review*, 89, 232-243.

- 2) Davis, J. R., & Botts, P. W. (2014). The rise of digital operations: The next frontier in innovation and competitiveness. *The McKinsey Quarterly*, 63(3), 1-12.
- 3) Davenport, T. H. (2013). *Process innovation: Rethinking work in the digital age*. Harvard Business Press.
- 4) Porter, M. E., & Heppelmann, J. (2014). How smart, connected products are transforming competition. *Harvard Business Review*, 92(11), 64-88.
- 5) Moegele, S., & Rabelo, R. (2017). The impact of digitalization on the automotive industry: An analysis of opportunities and challenges. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, 63, 47-63.
- 6) Gershon, M., & Prasad, S. (2016). *Managing business information systems: A case study approach*. John Wiley & Sons.
- 7) Laudon, K. L., & Laudon, J. P. (2019). *Information systems management: Surviving and thriving in a digital world*. Pearson.

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